

Employee Motivation and Job Performance of Selected Construction Companies in Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study was to investigate the relationship between employee motivation and job performance of selected construction companies in Rivers State. In this study, we have two variables employee motivation as the independent variable and job performances as the dependent variable. Both of these variables have their dimensions and measures which will assist the researcher to find out the relationship that employee motivation and job performances of selected construction companies in Rivers State, the methodology adopted was descriptive research design to collect both primary and secondary data. The population of this study consists of 100 (one hundred) staff in the selected construction companies in Rivers State. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire in four point likert scale. 100 copies of questionnaire were distributed to employees of selected construction companies in Rivers State which 90 was retrieved for the analysis. The test-re-test method was adopted in assessing the reliability of the study instrument. The data were analysed using t-test, while three hypotheses were tested using cronbach alpha with the help of Statistical tool to establish the significance of relationship between employee motivation and job performance of selected construction companies in Rivers State. From the above it was recommended that organizations should emphasize on induction training. Employee motivation plays a vital role in job performance. Management should evaluate employee suggestion scheme and use the feedback from the workforce to improve the company's environment and fulfill their needs and skills. People are different and they are motivated by diverse needs, such as physiological needs, safety requirements and self-actualization needs. Thus, managers should focus on reducing job dissatisfaction (working conditions, salary, supervision, relationship with employee), while using motivating factors such as achievement, recognition, promotion and conducive work environment. If employees feel appreciated for their work and are involved in decision-making, their enhanced enthusiasm and motivation will lead to better productivity and loyalty. The study recommends that Construction Companies should create better work environment, recognition and promotion for better job performance. The study recommends that Construction Companies should include employees in policy making which will boost their job performance.

Keywords-- Motivation, Employees, Job Performance, Promotion and Recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

Motivation is the most significant element for all organization private or a public zone. Motivations play a significant role for the accomplishment of any organization. The term motivation is basically derived from the word motive (Chaudhary & Sharma, 2012). So the meaning of the word motive is wants, desire, and needs of the peoples. Employee motivation is the procedure in which the organization should motivate their employee in the form of bonus, rewards, and some other incentives etc. only for the reason to attain the organizational objectives. The individual is a complex creature. So every employee in an organization is inspired by some various kind of tactic. According to Luthans (1998) explained that motivation is the procedure that energies, stimulates, stands, and directs actions and performance. Now a day's organization can simply transfer their services, goods, needs, and materials to some other countries or to some other organization. Human capital is the only one main asset which is not easily replaceable. Similarly, human resources are the most significant or very economical resources that cannot be replaceable for any organization.

Motivation is the one key element that impact the human capitals of any organization. So for the best performance or for the attaining of organizational objectives the organization should be motivating their workers. For better performance motivation is the greatest instruments. For managers employee motivation is one of the basic key tools to raise the efficient and effective management between the organization and employees (Shadare et al, 2009). According to Chowdhury, M.S (2006) motivation is the evolution of supporting and moving behavior of directed goals. Motivation is the inner

power that pushes employees to achieve the organizational and personal objectives (Reena et al, 2009).

In the field of psychology motivations is one of the most significant element and most supervisors who want highest production and output. The supervisors hold this with a better technique and motivate their workers in a good manner. Motivation is an operative tools that in the shape of administration in motivating the labour force. According to Dublin (1977) describes that motivation is the difficult powers that keep and maintain an individual's to continue effort in the organization. Siagian Sondra P (2004) defined that motivation is the energetic force that occurred when one participants of the organization wants and eager to apply in the shape of skill or expertise, time and effort to establish different events which they are answerable and accomplish their responsibility in the reason to attain the organization goals and objective that has been scheduled. According to Cole (2009) that motivation is basically about what energies an individual to work in a specific method with a certain quantity of determination.

Motivation is a pre disposition to perform in a purposive way to accomplish particular desires and needs (Buford et al, 1995). Motivation supports job satisfaction and increases the productivity of employees. One of the most significant elements is the determination that one lead to their aims. So this determination is known as motivation. This energy may originate from external or internal sources. The employees determents this and if the managers know that what kind of motivations inspire the employees to do work for them, so they can adapt job rewards and assignment to makes these employees impulse. One of the most significant motivational factors is the money asserted by Akintoye (2000).

The motivation tactics definitely accomplish the wants and needs of the workforce, and in returns the workers repay it through their hard work. Identifying the requirements and noticing it is the greatest important policy for each affiliation to gain the faithfulness of the employees (Chughtai, 2008). The classes of motivation are natural and extraneous.

Natural Motivation is an intellectual determination that chooses the development of a person's conduct as a significance of challenging or motivating job, defined extension to generate capabilities, proposing self-determination to do work, exposed entry to make and progress, and etc. Extraneous is similarly intellectual induce that adopts negotiating variation as an outcome of considerable and intangible revenue, such as, exceptional endowments, reimbursement, and subsidiary benefit. Motivation as the tactic in which desires, argues, striving, aspiration, explain or control the behaviour of human organisms (Dalton E. Farland, 2014). Previous studies have emphasized that motivation can affect the employee performance and job satisfaction. According to

Colquitt et al (2009), job performance is described as the value of the set of employee's behaviors that contributes either negatively or positively to achieve the organizational targets. The definition of job performance contains behaviors that are within the control of employees, but it places a border on the behavior are related to job performance.

Motivation will encourage the employees or workers of the organization will seriously do his/ her work and responsibilities (Azar & Shafiqhi, 2013). Good pay or salaries is also a valuable instrument to play a significant role to improving employee performance and also improve the productivity of an organization. Workers are the human resource to the organization and organizational success or failure depends on employee's performance within the organization. So the managers of organization should manage the resources efficiently and effectively to confirm the accomplishment. Motivations signify the difficult services and needs which provide the drive for employees to complete specific jobs (Shulze & Steyn, 2003). That employee who is motivated is always aware of the objective to be completed and leads his/ her determination at achieving that aim. In the organization motivation impact the employee performance especially those employee who have less skills they are motivated more and contribute 100 percent with the work.

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The research have examined that there are many elements that can impact employee motivation and job performance of organization, motivation is one of these elements. So our research studies will be used on the employee motivation and job performance. Work being formal or informal, paid or unpaid, plays a central role in the lives of people all across the world. While many jobs provide both income and personal satisfaction, they may also pose hazards and risks to health and safety. Among the public and private sector institutions in Nigeria, the construction industry can be seen as one of the oldest industries known to play a central role in the economic development of the country. Yet the construction industry has a problem of health-related illness and diseases where people are exposed to various toxic and harmful materials, including fuels, noise and metal dust. This study therefore aims to study the influence of employee motivation on job performance.

III. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To examine the effect of conducive work environment on job performance in selected construction companies in Rivers State.

2. To find out the relationship between Recognition and job performance in selected construction companies in Rivers State.
3. To examine the effect of promotion on job performance in selected construction companies in Rivers State.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Population of the Study

Population is a set of object or observations about which conclusion are drawn. The population of the study is 100 staff members which includes top level employees, middle level employees and low level employees. The amount of analysis is at the micro lewend thus individual based.

Table 3.1 Categories of the Target Population

Category	JULIUS BERGER	MCC	BENCO NIG LTD	Total
Top level employees	10	10	3	33
Middle level employees	2	3	1	6
Low level employees	25	15	11	71
Total	27	28	15	100

Source: (Human Resource desk, 2019)

Sampling Techniques

The sampling techniques that will be used in the research work is random sampling with a total population size 100 staff which will e used to compare their opinion in the company.

Method of Data Collection

The ultimate of every research is to find a solution to the identified problems of the subject of study, which can only be achieved through the collection of reliable data. In this research work, method of data collection will be both primary and secondary sources.

Primary Source of Data

These are firsthand information that will be used for the purpose of this project. This study makes use of the questionnaire and oral interview as a major source of primary data.

Secondary Source of Data

This refers to that information already in existence, having been collected originally for some other purposes. This includes the reviewing of articles that have to do with creativity, innovation and current journal, textbooks, Newspaper and internet.

Research Instrument

The research instrument for this study will be the questionnaire. According to Ojo (2005) questionnaire is a instrument containing some questions and statements (some with suggested alterative answers) for which the questions or confirm the statements. The questionnaire that will e used in the study will be divided in two sections. Section A contained information about the respondents that is their gender, marital status, age, educational qualification, years of working experience etc. Section B contained items on the

employee motivation and job performance. The second section that will be ranged from 5-1 point scale in the following pattern, strongly agree: 5, Agree: 4 undecided: 3, Disagree: 2 and Strongly Disagree: 1

Validity of the Research Instrument

A number of concepts are involved in a discussion of validity. Different types of validity have been identified. These include, the predictive validity which is the validity of an instrument to predict some future events, the concurrent validity which is usually measured y the calculation of a correction coefficient between the distribution of test scores and some concurrently existing criterion measure, the content validity which is essentially determined by the process through which the items were selected.

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics which includes frequencies, mean, standard deviation, Pearson product moment correction and percentages. Data collected was reported using frequency tables, pie charts and bar charts.

V. RESULTS

The chapter presents data pertinent to the research questions and hypotheses formulated to guide the study

5.1 Findings and Data Analysis

5.1.1 Gender of Respondents

The study involved gender distribution of respondents in order to answer the questionnaires providedas shown on the table.

Table 5.1: Gender of Respondents

Respondents	Frequency	Percent %
Female	20	22.22
Male	70	77.77
Total	90	100.0

Source: Researcher, 2019

Table 5.1 above depicts that 80% and 20 % of respondents of male and female respectively answered the questionnaires distributed.

5.1.2 Marital Status

The study involved gender distribution of respondents in order to answer the questionnaires provided as shown on the table.

Table 5.2: Gender of Respondents

Respondents	Frequency	Percent %
Single	20	22.22
Married	70	77.77
Divorced	0	0
Total	100	100.0

Table 5.2 above depicts that 77.77% and 22.22 % of respondents of single and married respectively answered the questionnaires distribute.

Table 5.3: Educational Level of Respondents

<i>Respondents</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent %</i>
<i>BS.C/HND</i>	55	61.11
<i>Master</i>	25	27.77
<i>Others</i>	10	11.11
<i>Total</i>	<i>90</i>	<i>100.0</i>

Source: Researcher, 2019

The others group constituted 11.11% of respondents followed by master with 22.77% and then the BS.C which made up 61.11% of the respondents.

Table 5.3: Year of Experience

Respondents	Frequency	Percent %
5-10years	15	16.66
10--15years	25	27.27
15-20years	40	50
20-30 years	10	11.11
Total	90	100.0

Source: Researcher, 2019

The 5-10 years of experiences constituted 16.66% of respondents, followed by 10-15 years within the range of 27.27% and then the range of 15-20 years of experiences which made up 50% of the respondents. The lowest

number of respondents was within the range of 20-30 years which made 11.11% of employees.

Research Question 1: To what extent does Conducive work environment relate to job performance in selected construction companies in Rivers State?

Table 5.1: Mean and Standard Deviation for Conducive work environment in job performance in selected construction companies in Rivers State

S/NO	Statement	X	STD	RMK
1	Security in my workplace is tight and commendable	3.34	0.87	A
2	Offices are well equipped and up to standard	3.20	0.76	A
3	Work environment is hygienic for staff	3.40	0.84	SA
4	There is room for staff training and development at my work place	3.04	0.85	A

Table 5.1 revealed that the conducive work environment range from 3.04-3.34 and standard deviation of 0.76-0.87. They all agreed to a high extent on the impact of conducive work environment in job performance of these selected construction companies in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: To what extent does recognition relate to job performance in these selected construction companies in Rivers State?

Table 5.2: Mean and Standard Deviation for recognition in job performance in selected construction companies in Rivers State

S/NO	Statement	X	STD	RMK
1	Worker are recognized when they do something outstanding at work	3.50	0.87	A
2	Promotion of staff every three years	3.40	0.85	A
3	Bonus is giving to each staff at the end of every year	3.20	0.84	SA
4	There are benefits for excellent work	3.50	0.76	A

Table 5.2 revealed that the recognition range from 3.20-3.50 and standard deviation of 0.76-0.87. They all agreed to a high extent on the impact of recognition in job

performance in these selected construction companies in Rivers State.

Research Question 3: To what extent does work quality relate to job performance in these selected construction companies in Rivers State?

Table 5.3: Mean and Standard Deviation for work quality related to job performance in selected construction companies in Rivers State

S/NO	Statement	X	STD	RMK
1	My work output meets set standards	3.30	0.76	A
2	I have good communication with my colleagues at work	3.50	0.84	SA
3	I have a better Knowledge of my job	3.20	0.83	A
4	I manager my time at work place effectively and efficiently	3.10	0.83	A

Table 5.3 revealed that the work quality range from 3.10-3.50 and standard deviation of 0.76-0.84. They all agreed to a high extent on the impact of work quality in job performance in these selected construction companies in Rivers State.

Research Question 4: To what extent does creativity relate to job performance in these selected construction companies in Rivers State?

Table 5.4: Mean and Standard Deviation of creativity related to job performance in selected construction companies in Rivers State

S/NO	Statement	X	STD	RMK
1	I generate noble ideas	3.02	0.87	A
2	I contribute in solving some problems at my work place	3.24	0.76	A
3	I am innovative in carrying out my job	3.40	0.83	A
4	I create new ideas within my team	3.50	0.82	A

Table 5.4 revealed that the creativity range from 3.02-3.50 and standard deviation of 0.76-0.87. They all agreed to a high extent on the impact of creativity in job performance in these selected construction companies in Rivers State.

observed that employee motivation and commitment are keys in job performance. Nevertheless, studies have shown that recognition boost productivity on the long term and also better rewards improve job performance significantly (Whitley, 2002). The study also found that there is a significant difference in Recognition and creativity of employees in selected construction companies in Rivers State.

VI. DISCUSSION OF THE FINDING

The study sought to examine the relationship between Employee Motivation and Job Performance of selected construction companies in Rivers State. Employees want to earn reasonable salaries, as money represents the most important incentive, when speaking of its influential value. Financial rewards have the capacity to maintain employee motivation towards higher job performance, especially workers from production and construction companies.

The study found out that, there is a significant difference in Conducive work environment and creativity of employees in selected construction companies in Rivers State.

The study also found out that there is a significant difference in conducive work environment and work quality of employees in selected construction companies in Rivers State. Moreover, there are other non-financial factors that have a positive influence on motivation, such as rewards, social recognition and performance feedbacks. It was

It was observed that recognition leads to job satisfaction, which in turn influence directly and positively the performance of employees. Moreover, recognition is one of the most efficient tools of management when trying to influence individual or group behavior, as to improve organization's effectiveness. The study found that there is a significant difference in Recognition and work quality of employees in selected construction companies in Rivers State. It was observed that high level of productivity is influenced by the level of motivation and effectiveness of the staff. Therefore, developing and implementing employee training programs is a necessary strategy to motivate workers. The study found that there is a significant difference in promotion and creativity of employees in selected construction companies in Rivers State. It was noticed that promotion is an important factor for an organization that wants to be successful, as it has the ability to enhance employees' motivation and foster interpersonal communication.

The study found that there is a significant difference in promotion and work quality of employees in selected construction companies in Rivers State. It was observed that promotion increase the level of work quality in the construction companies. The vast majority of companies use pay, promotion, bonuses and other types of reward to motivate employees and to increase their job performance. In order to use salary as a motivator, managers have to develop salary structures, according to the importance of each job, individual performance and special allowances. Employees can also be motivated through proper leadership, as leadership is all about getting things done the right way.

VII. CONCLUSION

Employee motivation plays a vital role in job performance in these selected construction companies that was carried out in Port Harcourt. Management should evaluate employee suggestion scheme and use the feedback from the workforce to improve the company environment and fulfill their needs and skills. People are different and they are motivated by diverse needs, such as physiological needs, safety requirements and self-actualization needs. Thus, focusing on employees at every level of the workforce and analyzing each department of the organization will provide detailed and accurate information regarding the needs of employees. A motivated and qualified workforce is essential for any company that wants to increase productivity, customer satisfaction and job performance. In this context, motivation means the willingness of an individual to put efforts in taking action towards companies's goals. The challenge for any manager is to find the means to create and sustain employee motivation. On one hand, managers should focus on reducing job dissatisfaction (working conditions, salary, supervision, relationship with employee), while using motivating factors such as achievement, recognition, promotion and conducive work environment. If employees feel appreciated for their work and are involved in decision-making, their enhanced enthusiasm and motivation will lead to better productivity and loyalty. The ability to attract, keep and motivate high-performance is becoming increasingly important in today's competitive company environments. At the end of the research, it was realized that the employee's working environment affect their productivity greatly. Therefore it is the responsibility of the managers to organize and provide a work friendly environment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings, the following recommendation was stated below

- 1) The study also recommends that Construction Companies should emphasize on induction training. This will help in clarifying the roles of employees thus improving the general job performance.
- 2) The study recommends that Construction Companies should create better work environment, recognition and promotion for better job performance.
- 3) The study recommends that Construction Companies should include employees in the companies' policy making which will boost their job performance.

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